

D4.5 Integrated Ecological-Socio-Economic Management Framework
ESE Step-by-Step guidance

Integrated Ecological-Socio-Economic Management Framework (ESE)

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Abstract	This deliverable presents the Ecosystem-based Spatial Evaluation (ESE) Framework developed within the MSP4BIO project. The

Keywords

ESE Framework provides a structured approach to support Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) processes with the aim to protect and restore biodiversity while balancing sustainable human uses at sea.

The document describes the key principles, main components, and practical steps of the framework, showing how it helps integrate ecological knowledge, spatial data, and stakeholder input. The deliverable includes a step-by-step guidance for applying the framework in real planning contexts, examples of methods and tools, and recommendations for future testing in pilot areas. Overall, it aims to support planners, authorities, and stakeholders in making informed decisions that strengthen the ecological coherence of MSP.

MSP, MPAs, Biodiversity inclusive, tool, guidance

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Table of contents

Table of contents	5
Acronyms/Glossary.....	8
Executive Summary.....	10
1 Introduction	11
2 Methodology	13
3 ESE framework.....	16
3.1 Management questions	16
3.2 Practices	21
3.2.1 Scoping.....	21
3.2.2 Data Collection and Presentation.....	23
3.2.3 Analysis and Diagnosis	24
3.2.4 Prioritisation and Designation.....	24
3.2.5 Implementation and Management.....	25
3.2.6 Monitoring and Evaluation.....	25
3.3 Modules.....	26
3.3.1 ESE 1 – Ecological Toolkit	26
3.3.2 ESE 2 - Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs	27
3.3.3 ESE 3 - Trade-offs method for protections and restoration in MSP	27
3.3.4 ESE 3 - Nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors	28
3.3.5 Policy solutions.....	31
3.3.6 Strategic guidance	32
3.4 Operational approaches	32
3.5 Answers	34
3.6 Application examples.....	35
3.6.1 Marine Mammals & CC: NW Mediterranean prioritization for 2030	36
3.6.2 Application of the HELCOM SPIA Tool for HELCOM MPAs	37

This publication was funded by the European Union. Its contents are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union.

3.6.3 An MPA redesign and enlargement proposal for the Graciosa Island Test Site	37
3.6.4 Integrated Management Framework Proposal for the Cadiz Bay Test Site	38
3.6.5 Integration of CEA in MSP by utilising PlanWise4Blue (ESE 1) - Bulgarian Black Sea test site	40
3.6.6 Prioritization and optimization for the identification of strictly protected Belgian MPAs	41
3.6.7 Deep-sea ecosystems conservation strategy in the NW Mediterranean: a blueprint for 10% of protection	42
4 Conclusive remarks	46
5 ESE Framework availability.....	48
6 References.....	49
Annex 1 – ESE framework downloadable document (on 25.07.2025)	51

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1 ESE framework conceptual model.</i>	<i>13</i>
<i>Figure 2 - Total number of questions identified per each of the four management needs defined for the scope of the ESE framework.</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>Figure 3 - Managment question properties: the histograms show the number of questions belonging to the different groups of features defined after clusterisation.</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Figure 4 - Example of conceptual diagram provided by the ESE framework for each answer.</i>	<i>35</i>

Acronyms/Glossary

Acronym	Meaning
ACCOBAMS	Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area
BPNS	Belgian Part of the North Sea
BRIDGE-BS	Advancing Black Sea Research and Innovation to Co-Develop Blue Growth within Resilient Ecosystems
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CC	Climate Change
CEA	Cumulative Effect Assessment
CoP	Communities of Practice, key stakeholders
DPSIR	Drivers, Pressures, State, Impact, Response
DST	Decision Support Tool
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EBM	Ecosystem-Based Management
EBSA	Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Areas
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ESE	Ecological-Socio-Economic framework
ESE1	ESE module 1- Ecological toolkit, a step-by-step guide, including improved ecological criteria and DSTs to support MPA prioritization and networking (D3.4)
ESE2	ESE module 2 - Socio-economic and governance criteria to support MPA prioritisation and networking (D4.1)
ESE3	ESE module 3 – Guide on strategic and spatial measures for blue economy sectors and Trade-offs method for marine protection in MSP (D4.2 and D4.3).
ESE practices	ESE structured methodology or approach designed to guide users in making informed decisions
ESE Admin	ESE Admin Interface
ESE Generator	ESE Generator
ESE Web Tool	ESE end-user Web Tool
ETP	Endangered, Threatened, and Protected species
FRA	Fishing Restricted Area

Acronym	Meaning
GES	Good Environmental Status
GFW	Global Fishing Watch
H2020	Horizon 2020
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IMMA	Important Marine Mammal Area
IMTA	Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture
ME	Management Effectiveness
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
MSPdF	Maritime Spatial Planning Data Framework
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NV	Nature Value
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OECM	Other Effective area-based Conservation Measure
SPZ	Special Protection Zone
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) Framework and its associated web tool, developed under the MSP4BIO project. The ESE Framework is a methodological guidance that help prioritize marine protection in MSP through several methodological steps and integrate social, economic, and ecological considerations. The Framework provides a structured approach to support decision-makers and stakeholders in incorporating ecosystem-based considerations into planning processes in a flexible, participatory, and modular way.

The deliverable outlines the methodological foundations of the framework, including the rationale for its conceptualization, the co-design process involving project partners and Communities of Practice established in the six test sites of MSP4BIO, and the iterative content development approach supported by a purpose-built web infrastructure. The framework is based on three main modules: ESE 1 addressing ecological elements, ESE 2 addressing socio-economic elements, and ESE3 addressing trade-offs between marine conservation and blue economy developments. The ESE comprises the following main components: the ESE Admin interface, designed for contributors to structure and manage content; the ESE Generator, a custom-built software that compiles and transforms content into final outputs; and the ESE Web Tool, a dynamic interface for end users to explore the guidance through multiple thematic pathways.

The framework has been designed to be lightweight yet scalable, enabling easy updates, contextual adaptations, and future expansion. It supports transferability to other governance contexts and offers a robust foundation for integrating new management questions, analytical and management practices (other than the actual ESE modules), and stakeholder inputs over time. Key strengths include its modularity, its ability to link management questions with tools and practices, and the collaborative approach underpinning its development. Limitations include the current simplicity of the interface and its reliance on continuous content enrichment. Nevertheless, the framework represents a promising solution for enhancing the accessibility and usability of socio-ecological guidance in marine and coastal planning, contributing to more resilient and inclusive ocean governance.

1 Introduction

MSP4BIO is a 3-year Horizon Europe project aiming to develop an innovative and flexible Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) Management Framework for protecting and restoring marine ecosystems. The project builds on, and integrates, existing knowledge and results from multiple origins, including other relevant projects and initiatives. In particular the key results include different modules developed during the project: the ecological toolkit - ESE1 ([Kotta et al., 2024 – Deliverable D3.4](#)), the climate-smart MPA guidance (Cambra et al., 2024 – Deliverable D3.3), socio-economic criteria ([Pegorelli et al., 2023, Deliverable D4.1](#)), trade-off scenarios analysis ([Gutierrez et al., 2024 – Deliverable D4.3](#)) and the Guideline for the strategic and spatial measures – Sectorial sheets ([Pegorelli et al., 2024 D4.2](#)) and policy coherence criteria used to develop solutions ([Pinarbasi et al., 2025 – Deliverable 6.2](#)).

ESE is methodological guidance that help prioritize marine protection in MSP through several methodological steps and integrate social, economic, and ecological considerations

The ESE Framework integrates and organizes all the information with the aim to support the spatial planning and management of coastal, offshore, and deep-sea ecosystems in times of accelerated changes. The framework identifies an improved set of biodiversity and climate-related prioritisation criteria for MPAs based on the best available scientific knowledge to date and will link this environmental knowledge with socio-economic considerations.

Moreover, as adopted in the whole project, the ESE Framework builds on a socially innovative participatory approach through the co-development with the Communities of Practice (CoPs) at each test site, with the aim of improving awareness and confidence of planners.

This deliverable presents the ESE Framework, a methodological step-by-step guidance to support identification of MPAs and help strengthening inclusion of biodiversity protection in MSP.

The deliverable is organized in three sections: Chapter 2 presents the methodology, outlining the rationale behind the conceptualisation of the ESE Framework, the co-design process, and the iterative content development carried out through interactive sessions and feedback loops with project partners and stakeholders from test sites, as well as the approach adopted for the development of the ESE Web Tool. Chapter 3 introduces the ESE Framework itself, detailing its conceptual model, the core components, and the potential interrelations among them. Chapter 4 provides concluding remarks, summarising the main strengths, limitations, and future development opportunities of the framework, including its potential for transferability to other contexts and its adaptability to new policy questions and user needs over time.

Even if not included in the Grant Agreement (GA) of MSP4BIO, a web version of the ESE framework was also produced, and it is available at ese.tools4.msp.eu. The

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web version represents the complete version of the ESE framework, providing a step-by-step guidance, a full set of answers to relevant management questions and application examples in test sites (for more details see also D5.3, [Stancheva et al., 2025](#)). The full content of the web version is also provided as a downloadable guidance document, included in Annex 1 of this deliverable.

2 Methodology

The conceptual model underlying the guidance was developed by collecting and structuring information from all project work packages, with the goal of establishing a coherent and operational framework. The process of defining the conceptual model also served as a harmonization process, promoting alignment among work packages and encouraging the adoption of a common terminology in relation to criteria, tools, and other core elements. The resulting structure consists of clearly defined components that articulate a primary flow of information, while also incorporating interconnections that allow users to explore the information from different perspectives and contexts. The conceptual model of the ESE framework is illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 1 ESE framework conceptual model.

A key feature of the ESE conceptual model is its **user-centred perspective**, ensuring that information flows are initiated by users and structured around their management needs.

The **primary users of this guidance** include MSP authorities, planners, environmental authorities, MPA managers, decision makers, sector stakeholders and all users interested in identifying and managing MPAs as well as those interested in strengthening biodiversity protection in MSP.

Users' needs are translated through specific management questions. Such questions were identified, gathered and discussed across all activities undertaken under WP5 with

the CoPs members of each test-sites of the project. Users were deeply involved for the entire duration of the project activities in the ESE development, testing and validation throughout 4-5 rounds of interactions (see D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.5). The four CoP interactions, consisting of interviews and dedicated workshops, served distinct and progressive objectives: (1) confirm test site priorities and needs, collect information on data availability, and identify remaining data gaps; (2) define management questions to support the definition of the ESE methodology; (3) support participatory mapping and test the trade-off methodology within the ESE framework; (4 and 5) validate the initial draft of the ESE framework and the site-specific solutions developed through its application in the test sites.

As part of the methodology for operationalising the ESE Framework, **a dedicated web-based tool was developed** to support the creation, organisation, and delivery of the ESE guidance in a dynamic and accessible format. The tool was designed to be lightweight and modular, ensuring ease of use, flexibility in content exploration, and low maintenance requirements, while remaining fully aligned with the ESE conceptual model.

The ESE Framework is based on three main components:

ESE Admin: This is the back-end interface, primarily intended for project partners and contributors responsible for developing the ESE modules. The admin interface allows the structured input and organisation of various content elements, such as key questions, answers, practices, modules, criteria, and links to relevant tools or external resources (e.g., datasets, StoryMaps). All content is stored in a relational database that reflects the interconnected nature of the ESE conceptual model. The interface was co-designed with technical partners and content developers to ensure usability and consistency across modules.

ESE Generator: This custom-developed software component connects directly to the content database, processes the structured information, and generates the final outputs of the guidance. It builds both the interactive web interface and a consolidated PDF version of the guidance, ensuring that users can access the content in multiple formats. In addition, the Generator automatically creates conceptual diagrams (see Figure 4) for each answer. These diagrams visually represent the relationships among ESE elements such as questions, answers, modules, practices, and policy solutions. The Generator can be run manually or scheduled to automatically update the outputs as new content is added, or existing elements are modified.

ESE Web Tool: This is the user-facing, interactive interface generated by the ESE Generator. It is designed for end users who wish to explore the ESE guidance through multiple, intuitive entry points, such as thematic areas, decision-support needs, or specific policy questions. The interface guides users through various content pathways, helping them to navigate the complex structure of the ESE Framework in a flexible and accessible way. Despite the richness of the content, the tool remains lightweight and easy to navigate, making it suitable for a wide range of users, including policymakers, practitioners, and researchers.

The technological stack used to implement the tool includes:

- Django (<https://www.djangoproject.com/>), for managing the admin interface (ESE Admin) and content architecture;
- Sphinx (<https://www.sphinx-doc.org/>), for generating the web-based interface for users;
- ESE Generator, a python module developed within the MSP4BIO project, to automate the integration and publication of content. It uses PlantUML for generating conceptual diagrams, an open-source tool that allows dynamic generation of UML-like diagrams from simple text descriptions.

This infrastructure enabled a collaborative and iterative content development process, where project partners and pilot area stakeholders contributed to the guidance through structured inputs and feedback loops, ensuring that the tool is both scientifically robust and practically relevant.

3 ESE framework

The ESE is a **methodological step-by-step guidance** designed to help prioritise marine protection within MSP by providing a sequence of methodological steps that integrate social, economic, and ecological considerations.

The primary users of this guidance include MSP authorities, planners, environmental authorities, MPA managers, decision makers, sector stakeholders and all users interested in identifying and managing MPAs as well as those interested in strengthening biodiversity protection in MSP.

The guidance assembles practical and workable solutions, comprising a set of best practices, criteria, datasets, methods, tools, policy solutions, and strategic approaches. These are drawn from the outcomes generated by the MSP4BIO project and beyond and are intended to assist users in applying integrated approaches to marine protection.

The guidance is accessible as a web-based tool (www.esetools4msp.eu), reflecting the project's broader objective to provide practical instruments rather than just written documents.

Importantly, **the web-based tool allows the framework to become a “living guidance” system: it is open to continuous updates and improvements as new knowledge, data, and tools become available, ensuring that management responses remain relevant, adaptive, and informed by best practices at national, regional, and international levels.**

3.1 Management questions

As a necessary step to provide a logical backbone to the ESE framework, well rooted in the users' needs, a structured process was designed across WP4 and WP5: the test site teams together with CoPs, were engaged to identify (pre-select and prioritize) both broad **management needs** and specific **management questions** relevant to each test site. Key elements regarding the framing of the questions per se (e.g. level of detail, vocabulary used) and their purposes (e.g. interconnection with ecological, social or economic component, management tool promoted, selected target) were commonly evaluated discussed and prioritized with CoPs in each test site. This collaborative exercise revealed a diverse and heterogeneous collection of needs and questions, covering policy, governance, ecological issues, and climate change concerns.

To manage this diversity, a comprehensive exercise of harmonisation was carried out, involving the cleaning of terminology, identification of overlaps, and grouping of related questions. In total, 52 management questions were collected and systematically organised. The questions were structured hierarchically, starting with general issues such as *how to prioritise areas for conservation*, and moving toward more specific topics, including the *identification of priority areas for pelagic biodiversity* or the *integration of fisheries*

reform considerations. The structuring of these questions was key to harmonising terminology across the project's work packages and aligning efforts around a common framework.

Each question was also assigned to one of four broader management needs (definitions are also provided):

- **Strengthening conservation:** this management need includes, in its scope, the identification of valuable/vulnerable areas, the assessment of cumulative impacts of human activities on marine ecosystems, the identification and designation of new MPAs, MPAs enlargement, MPAs effectiveness assessment, the improvement of connectivity within existing MPA networks, including Climate Change-related considerations, and restoration. Monitoring related issues are also considered when referring to conservation
- **Balancing between economics and conservation:** this management need includes, in its scope, the consideration of socio-economic aspects in MPA establishment or enlargement. This also encompasses ensuring that trade-offs between maritime economy and conservation are identified or improved (eventually as part of the MSP process), potentially including the identification of compensation measures.
- **Integrated management of marine ecosystems:** this management need involves, in its scope, improving the management of marine ecosystems and their services as part of an MPA and/or MSP process, including strengthening the sustainability of maritime activities and enhancing compatibility between uses and marine protection.
- **Stakeholder engagement, participation, and co-creation:** this management need involves, in its scope, ensuring stakeholders are engaged in the planning process for MPA and/or MSP, including promoting their participation in the co-creation of solutions to enhance ecosystem and biodiversity protection (e.g. co-management of MPAs).

Each question can be relevant for one or more management needs. The overall number of questions per management need is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Total number of questions identified per each of the four management needs defined for the scope of the ESE framework.

Additionally, each question was associated with several "properties" to facilitate structured analysis and use. These properties included:

- Question level (three levels of detail in scope: general, specific, very specific)
- Marine zones (coastal zone, offshore area, deep sea)
- Spatial scale (national, regional/local, transboundary/sea basin)
- User type (sector stakeholders, marine planners, MSP authorities, MPA managers, environmental authorities)
- Relevant MSP stages (e.g., assessing context and defining a vision, elaborating the plan, monitoring)

The distribution of questions across these properties, illustrated in Figure 3, demonstrates their scope and diversity. Most questions were linked to strengthening conservation and integrated management of marine ecosystems, with frequent associations to MSP stages such as plan elaboration, monitoring, and implementation. Furthermore, questions addressed different marine zones — with coastal and offshore areas most represented — and all spatial scales from local to transboundary contexts. The association with user types ensures that the questions are practical and relevant for diverse audiences, including planners, authorities, managers, environmental agencies, and sector stakeholders.

Overall, this structured, and user-centred approach ensures that the guidance provides targeted and operational answers to management questions, aligned with the needs of MSP processes across varied geographic, ecological, and governance contexts.

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Test sites

Question levels (1: general, 2: specific, 3: very specific)

Spatial scales

Target groups

Marine zones

MSP stages

Figure 3 - Management question properties: the histograms show the number of questions belonging to the different groups of features defined after clusterisation.

3.2 Practices

Built on common steps, the ESE Practices serve as a cohesive backbone for integrating diverse modules, approaches, and tools. Within the ESE framework, the term Practice refers to a structured methodology or approach designed to guide users in making informed decisions. A Practice provides possible ways of addressing specific management questions, supporting decision-making through the systematic organization and application of relevant knowledge, tools, and criteria.

While some Practices describe straightforward procedures, others may involve more complex processes consisting of multiple cycles of interaction, intermediate phases, and the combination of sub-practices. Practices may recommend criteria and indicators, explain how to combine them, and provide documentation on interpretation, such as thresholds or weighting schemes. They can also suggest decision-support tools to facilitate robust and evidence-based decision-making.

Importantly, Practices are mapped onto key stages of the decision-making cycle, supporting activities from Scoping, through Data collection and presentation, Analysis and diagnosis, Prioritisation and designation, Implementation and management, and culminating in Monitoring and evaluation. Stakeholder engagement is considered as transversal theme among all practices. This structure ensures that Practices contribute to a comprehensive, systematic, and iterative approach to environmental and socio-economic management.

The ESE Framework includes the following practices being at the core of the step-by-step approach offered by the guidance:

1. Scoping
2. Data collection and presentation
3. Analysis and diagnosis
4. Prioritisation and designation
5. Implementation and management
6. Monitoring and evaluation

3.2.1 Scoping

This practice aims to support the identification of the scope of the problem, with reference to the management needs and the specific management question(s). This includes the identification of the geographic scope and boundaries of the area of interest, the temporal scale the management question refers to, and the identification of the test site's main ecological, governance, social, and economic key elements, depending on the topic(s) addressed by the management question(s). The deep understanding of ecological significance, biodiversity values, and the socio-economic importance of MPAs (or candidate ones) in the area are also supported by this practice.

The practice further involves the identification of key stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, NGOs, MSP planners, researchers, MPA managers,

and coastal and maritime sectors. This practice helps identify all the key elements to be considered in the analysis. These elements should come from a priority-setting exercise from CoP members and all stakeholders involved at each stage of the thinking-process, where only those deemed truly significant are selected.

In the scoping phase, the following steps should be undertaken:

- Analysis of the management question: Identification of keywords within the question, such as climate change, sensitivity to human impacts, connectivity, vulnerable marine ecosystems, pelagic species, etc.
- Definition of management objective: Identification of the management objective, e.g., the design of a new MPA, the expansion of an existing MPA, management of existing MPAs, or design of a network of MPAs.
- Definition of the management approach: The approach is defined as either conservative, i.e., applying strict protection based on current scientific and empirical knowledge and limiting the impact of uncertainty on the effectiveness of protection (e.g., promoting the conservation of the whole list of vulnerable species), or selective, i.e., more pragmatic, taking into account the limited means of ensuring ecological protection and the difficulty of making management trade-offs between conservation and human activities, particularly in heavily used coastal areas (e.g., conserve 75% of the species most likely to survive in an area, conserve flagship species, among others).
- Definition of the context scale: Define whether the scope is at MSP, MPA networks or MPA level.
- Definition of socio-economic status and its future developments: Define human uses with societal benefits and those to be carefully managed to balance ecological conservation, define actual human pressure and foreseen activities/threats.
- Definition of the geographical area: Define the geographical boundaries or sea basin, possibly delimited by geographical coordinates (including depth, latitude and longitude, if available).
- Definition of the spatial scale: The spatial scale depends on the conservation objective, whether it is focused on one or more MPAs, networks of MPAs, at sub-national, national, or transboundary scales.
- Definition of the temporal scale: The temporal scale is particularly important in the context of climate change, spanning decades to centuries.
- Stakeholder engagement: Actively involve stakeholders, including local communities, scientists, government agencies, and non-governmental organisations, throughout the scoping process. Gather feedback on proposed MPA designs, address concerns, and ensure transparency in decision-making.

3.2.2 Data Collection and Presentation

This practice is based on the results of the previous step/practice (Scoping) and involves gathering and organising all data related to the previously identified species/habitats, selecting macro-criteria and inner criteria related to different methodological strategies, and all additional information (e.g., human activities, exogenous and endogenous drivers) necessary to support the subsequent phases (e.g., Analysis and Diagnosis, Prioritisation). The objective of this practice is to standardise the information, making it easy to analyse and present in an accessible format.

For the collection of information, it is proposed to follow the approach presented by the MSP Data Framework (MSPdF) and subsequently extended and adapted. The framework, initially developed to support MSP processes, can more generally be considered suitable for supporting different types of area-based design and management processes. These processes require the collection of spatial data and information related to a great variety of issues and themes.

When facing the data collection task, it is necessary to answer questions such as:

- What type of data should be collected and included in the analysis for suitability zoning of economic activities, Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA), or land-sea interactions?
- What are the relevant maritime and coastal uses?
- What type of information needs to be collected within the socio-economic and governance topics?

By utilising the MSPdF, practitioners can address these questions and ensure that the data collection process is comprehensive, systematic, and aligned with the objectives of the MPA design and management. This framework provides guidance on defining relevant spatial data, identifying key issues and processes, and integrating socio-economic and governance considerations into the data collection and analysis process.

The MSPdF emphasises organising the collection of information into thematic clusters to facilitate effective data collection and management. We present a modified version of the MSPdF, which also introduces the Ecosystem Services cluster:

- Marine & Coastal Environment
- Marine & Coastal Conservation and Designated sites
- Oceanographic characteristics and Climate
- Coastal Land use and Planning
- Operational maritime activities and Maritime Spatial Planning
- Socio-economic information
- Ecosystem Services

- Governance information

Within each cluster, the MSPdF also proposes detailed approaches for the classification and categorisation of information.

- Stakeholder engagement: Actively involve stakeholders, including local communities, scientists, government agencies, and non-governmental organisations, in the collection of data.

3.2.3 Analysis and Diagnosis

This practice supports the analysis of the current state of the marine environment and the understanding of the key ecological processes at play. The diagnosis includes understanding the cause-effect relationships, starting from pressures (deriving from human activities and climate change), determining the state (of marine ecosystems and biodiversity), and eventually impacts (already in place or possible, at present and/or in the future).

3.2.4 Prioritisation and Designation

Based on the results of previous practices — Scoping, Data Management, Analysis & Diagnosis — priorities are established for conservation, MPA identification, and management actions within the MPA.

This practice supports the identification of critical areas or habitats that require protection and supports their designation, either wholly or partially, as MPAs.

The practice includes the following steps:

- Defining priority sets: Utilise stakeholders' inputs, expert knowledge, and ecological criteria to establish conservation and management priorities for the MPA. This involves identifying the most critical areas or habitats for protection based on conservation goals and ecological significance.
- Applying conservation algorithms: Use conservation planning software that employs mathematical algorithms to identify priority areas for protection. These tools optimise the selection of protected areas to maximise biodiversity representation and ecological connectivity while considering spatial constraints and conservation targets. The algorithms rely on spatial data layers representing biodiversity features, habitat suitability, ecological processes, and conservation constraints. Additionally, socio-economic data, such as economic value, land tenure, and cultural significance, can be integrated to guide decision-making and ensure a balance between ecological and socio-economic objectives.
- Analysing results: Evaluate the outputs generated by conservation algorithms to identify potential MPA configurations that best align with conservation goals and priority sets. Assess the spatial distribution of selected areas and their ecological significance within the broader marine landscape.

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Actively involve stakeholders, including local communities, scientists, government agencies, and non-governmental organisations, throughout the prioritisation process. Gather feedback on proposed MPA designs, address concerns, and ensure transparency in decision-making.
- **Iterative refinement:** Continuously refine the prioritisation analysis based on stakeholder feedback, newly available data, and evolving conservation objectives. Regularly update and improve MPA designations to adapt to changing ecological conditions and management needs.

3.2.5 Implementation and Management

Implementation of an MSP plan or of an MPA is based on the control of human activities. Such control can be realized by:

- Establishing area boundaries for specific activities, i.e., zoning, including defining Strong Protection Zones (SPZ) or no-take zones (NTZ).
- Enforcing closure during parts of the year critical to the life history of certain species, or for longer periods.
- Setting limits to fisheries (e.g. engine and gears limitations, fish individual minimum and maximum catch sizes or bag-limits, closures) .
- Prohibiting or limiting destructive practices.
- Issuing permits to control or limit the number of participants engaged in a form of use such as limiting access by setting a carrying capacity which may not be exceeded.

It is also essential to control activities outside the MPA boundaries that may affect the long-term viability of the MPA. Some control can be achieved by the creation of contiguous terrestrial protected areas. Local government have an important role to play in controlling development and other activities in adjacent coastal areas, as a form of integrated coastal management.

3.2.6 Monitoring and Evaluation

Most MPAs have management plans that set goals and objectives, guiding the evaluation of MPA management effectiveness (ME). Monitoring and assessment play a key role in informing short- and medium-term management decisions and contribute to broader national and international assessments, such as those for the European Union (EU) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

Monitoring programs should provide consistent data over time, relying on MPA staff, consultants, NGOs, and researchers. While periodic monitoring exists, management agencies often favour qualitative assessments based on expert interpretation rather than quantitative analyses because of the lack of clear lecture grid and accurate quantitative thresholds but also of competence or manpower. However, there is growing interest in better utilizing monitoring data for condition assessments.

The process from monitoring to assessment and final knowledge dissemination is often poorly documented, making it difficult for MPA managers and policymakers to integrate scientific findings effectively. Many MPAs do not use monitoring-based data for management decisions, highlighting the need for stronger connections between science and policy. At regional and global levels, strategic linkages are required to ensure ocean observations inform policies. In the EU, implementing an ecosystem-based approach demands better integration of science, policy, and society, in line with CBD recommendations.

3.3 Modules

The ESE Framework is based on several Modules, developed within the MSP4BIO project and tested in the test sites. The framework includes the following modules:

- ESE1 - Ecological Toolkit (including a portfolio of improved ecological criteria and DSTs)
- ESE2 - Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs
- ESE3 - Trade-offs method for protections and restoration in MSP + ESE3 - Nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors.

In addition to that, the ESE framework also integrates, data, geoportals story maps, and conservation criteria mentioned in official initiatives and policies (from WP2), policy solutions (from WP6), and Strategic guidance (from WP4).

The knowledge from the above components is made available through the Practices – as described in the previous paragraph, that users can follow in order to address their questions through the application of ecological and socio-economic criteria and tools.

3.3.1 ESE 1 – Ecological Toolkit

ESE1, the Ecological Toolkit (D3.4), improves decision-making processes for MPAs by helping to prioritise proposed protected areas, integrate connectivity processes and assess the impacts of human activities on marine ecosystems for, both, current and future scenarios. The Toolkit provides a range of solutions and a comprehensive step-by-step guide to help decision-makers navigate the complex processes of MPA prioritisation and connectivity for the designation of MPA networks. ESE1 integrates a set of ecological criteria extracted from environmental initiatives and policies,

enhanced ecological and climate-related criteria derived from systematic reviews and desktop analyses as outlined in MSP4BIO project WP2 (D2.2) and WP3 (D3.2). It further encompasses guidance on incorporating climate change scenarios into protection and prioritisation strategies for the development of climate-smart MPAs and MSP, as detailed in D3.3.

This comprehensive approach will ensure that MPAs are designed and managed with the latest ecological knowledge and climate-smart principles. Based on a curated set of ecological criteria, this guide follows through the essential steps of vulnerability assessment for prioritising conservation actions in MPAs. It provides methodologies that equip stakeholders with the tools to develop conservation scenarios that are resilient and adaptive to climate change.

3.3.2 ESE 2 - Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs

ESE2 (D4.1) provides socio-economic and governance criteria to support the prioritisation of proposals for new MPAs, revised MPA boundaries, reallocations, and more. Collectively, these criteria provide a framework for considering the MSP process and ensuring a comprehensive approach to decision-making and integration of biodiversity protection in planning. Regarding governance criteria, ESE2 is based on a common regulatory framework at the EU level, which leads to a homogenization in prioritising them across different sites. These criteria are generic and strategic for any MSP process, as well as for the designation or management of an MPA.

This part of ESE2 presents, among the steps of an MSP process, the implementation of strategic planning, as well as the need for adaptive management through monitoring and feedback. Regarding the socio-economic criteria, these are expected to vary in relevance for the different sites. The relevance of socio-economic criteria depends on site-specific aspects such as national and local objectives, and the nature, health and functioning of the ecosystem under protection. ESE2 also provides links between socio-economic criteria and ecosystem services. This component is of particular importance to be used in stakeholder consultation at site level, when comparing alternative scenarios for MPAs, within and outside of MSP processes.

3.3.3 ESE 3 - Trade-offs method for protections and restoration in MSP

ESE3 (D4.3) provides a guideline for the participatory creation of integrated trade-off scenarios. Scenario-building to explore trade-offs can help to improve the management of marine spaces and safeguard ecosystem services. These scenarios aim to assess and negotiate the consequences of diverse actions and strategies regarding the spatial and strategic management of marine areas.

The key element of the approach is to understand how various human activities can influence ecosystem services and vice versa to define a knowledge-based ground for negotiating solutions. The outcomes, particularly the trade-off scenario guidelines, can be integrated into practical tools and frameworks, aiding decision-making processes related to marine resource management.

Effective management of trade-offs involves stakeholder engagement, scientific analysis, and the utilisation of Decision-Support Tools (DST) to pinpoint optimal solutions that minimise negative impacts while maximising overall benefits. Trade-offs manifest in close association with specific goals, interests, and activities.

Various types of trade-offs can be categorised:

- Trade-off between conservation and economic development objectives: MSP necessitates a delicate equilibrium between safeguarding marine ecosystems and supporting economic activities such as fishing, shipping, and tourism. For instance, the designation of MPAs can restrict opportunities for fishing and tourism, affecting the monetary revenue generated from these activities.
- Trade-off between short-term and long-term benefits: MSP must balance the immediate gains of specific activities and the long-term benefits of preserving marine ecosystems. For instance, permitting oil and gas exploration and drilling may offer short-term economic benefits but could produce irreversible impacts the environment and marine life.
- Trade-off between exclusive and shared uses: decision-making on allocating marine space may involve trade-offs between exclusive use for a specific activity or multiple shared uses. This requires the consideration of diverse stakeholders' interests and balancing activities like fishing, recreational zones, shipping lanes and conservation activities.
- Trade-off between specific stakeholder interests: divergent priorities and objectives among stakeholders, including fishermen, local communities, conservation organisations, researchers, maritime tour operators, and non-governmental organisations, necessitate trade-offs to accommodate varied perspectives.
- Trade-offs between local and regional interests: while MSP can benefit local communities through economic development and job creation, it must also account for the impact of human activities on the global ocean ecosystem.

3.3.4 ESE 3 - Nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors

This component of ESE 3 (D4.2) provide a non-exhaustive list of good management practices – named in the framework as Measures - for each of the five blue economy sectors considered by the MSP4BIO project: aquaculture, fisheries, marine non-living resources, renewable energy, and tourism. Such Measures may serve as a guide to fostering responsible and sustainable practices that support both economic interests and environmental conservation.

Within the framework, measures are grouped by sector and by typology. Groups by typology are shown in the following list:

MPA - Development of the activity

- Environmentally friendly label
- Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA)
- Organic fish farming regulations
- Fishing practices limits
- Optimized land use
- Collaborative farming initiatives

MPA - Limiting the activity

- Target species' restrictions
- Closed areas and seasons
- Irregular closures for periodic harvesting
- Changes in permitted activities
- Minimum size/weight restrictions for fishing
- Static gear
- Membership of fishing cooperative
- Fisheries management recognizing traditional knowledge
- Industrial fishery restrictions

MPA - Management process

- Local knowledge
- Assessment of plans and projects
- Adaptive Risk Management
- Comprehensive investigations
- Habitat Feature Sensitivity Matrices
- Ecosystem Service Tools
- Implement effective monitoring practices
- Facilitate stakeholder engagement
- Buffer zones
- Avoid major migration corridors and sensitive habitats

MPA - Socio-ecosystem

- Local knowledge
- Assessment of plans and projects
- Comprehensive investigations
- Ecosystem Service Tools
- Living infrastructure with ecological community
- Fishing practices limits
- Optimized land use
- Facilitate stakeholders' engagement
- Criteria for fishing permissions

- Buffer zones
- Membership of fishing cooperative
- Fisheries management recognizing traditional knowledge
- Avoid major migration corridors and sensitive habitats

MSP - Development of the activity

- Sea Garden Community
- Environmental performance reports
- Code of Good Practices
- Agreement among artisanal fish farming
- Temporary reserve area
- Study the environment
- Inclusive design
- Circular Economy
- New solutions
- Minimize sediment resuspension and noise
- Burying/shielding cables
- Quantitative analysis
- Voluntary Initiative for Information Sharing
- Nature enhancement
- Burying submarine cables
- Vegetable-based hydraulic fluids
- Vulnerable species assessment
- Minimizing the use of slack or loose tether
- Long lifespan of structures
- Noise-deflecting devices
- Use of new devices
- Gear marking
- Notify authority in advance
- Alternative installation methods
- Bird-scaring lines or Tori lines
- Grid connections
- Turbine layouts

MSP - Limiting the activity

- Exclusion zones in archaeological features
- Exclusion zones for sensitive features
- Protocols of safe operation
- Safety distance from ecologically valuable areas
- Physical barriers
- Closed areas to different levels of fishing

- Benthic protection areas banning bottom trawling

MSP - Management process

- Educational awareness
- Environmental performance reports
- Plan and implement protected areas
- Seabed mapping
- Ensure no adverse effects
- Code for environmental management
- Decommission
- Regional Environmental Management Plans
- Protocols of safe operation
- Mapping habitats
- Involvement of local communities
- Vessels mapping updated cartography
- Sensitivity maps
- Zoning scheme
- Benthic protection areas banning bottom trawling

MSP - Socio-ecosystem

- Educational awareness
- Seabed mapping
- Ensure no adverse effects
- Study the environment
- Inclusive design
- Means for the returning of a species
- Decommission
- Regional Environmental Management Plans
- Nature enhancement
- Long lifespan of structures
- Mapping habitats
- Involvement of local communities
- Sensitivity maps
- Closed areas to different levels of fishing

3.3.5 Policy solutions

Through an iterative, stakeholder-driven process, MSP4BIO [Deliverable D6.2](#) identified policy solutions addressing institutional coordination, policy integration, stakeholders' involvement, funding mechanisms, capacity building, and technical support at the national, regional, and EU levels. These solutions were developed in collaboration with project partners, tested through country-specific engagements, and validated through regional

and EU-level discussions, including think tank meetings and contributions from the stakeholders. The following policy solutions are included in the ESE framework:

- Establishing a dedicated coordination framework for marine biodiversity
- Utilizing existing groups to establish compulsory biodiversity assessment and reporting mechanisms
- Revise MPAs objectives and involve MSP authorities in a consultative capacity
- Creating continuous input channels for stakeholders' engagement in policymaking
- Create mandatory, clear measures connecting human activities with biodiversity goals
- Strengthening MSP's role in achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) through capacity building, trainings and dialogue
- Developing comprehensive guidelines and enforcement mechanisms for effective MPA management
- Climate-smart maritime spatial planning in EU countries
- Allocating maritime tax revenue for national biodiversity strategy
- Increase investment in biodiversity research and monitoring for improved policy evaluation
- Investing in data collection and decision support tools for planning and monitoring
- Applying the policy solutions in the Cadiz Bay.

3.3.6 Strategic guidance

The Strategic guidance (D4.4) helps integrate MPAs within MSP processes across diverse governance scales and marine ecosystems. It is based on a structured screening process that includes (1) an expert judgment phase and (2) a criteria checklist to facilitate MPA integration throughout the entire MSP lifecycle — from plan preparation to implementation, monitoring, and revision phases. The proposed criteria are derived from current practices within EU Member States (MS), which have guided MSP development and evaluate whether and how MPAs are integrated into these processes. Four primary relationships between MPAs and MSP are identified: (1) Conservation as a driver for MSP; (2) Full integration of conservation into MSP; (3) Integration through Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA); (4) Conservation as a layer in MSP. Key considerations for successful integration include policy frameworks, identification of MPA networks, spatial analysis, stakeholder engagement, ecosystem-based management, adaptive management, capacity building, evaluation, and compliance with SEA requirements. The document Strategic guidance emphasises the importance of stakeholders' involvement and feedback throughout the MSP process to enhance collaboration and efficacy in the integration of MPAs into marine planning frameworks.

3.4 Operational approaches

In the ESE framework the term Operational approach is used as an umbrella concept including both the methods that can be applied to answer management needs/questions, and the tools - based on the methods - that represent practical instruments that can be

applied to specific cases (e.g. models, applications, databases). Example: Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) is a method to assess cumulative impacts on marine ecosystems. Some tools are available based on CEA: e.g. Tools4MSP CEA, HELCOM SPIA tool, Planwise4Blue. In MSP4BIO, the tools are also referred to as Decision Support Tools (DSTs). Both the method and the tools are named as Operational approaches in the context of this Guidance.

The ESE framework considers the following operational approaches, articulated in Core methods, Methods and Tools:

Core methods

A (Core) Method is one approach that can be used to answer management needs/questions. Based on a method, tools can be developed representing practical instruments that can be applied to specific cases (e.g. models, applications, data bases).

- Dispersion and connectivity modelling
- Cumulative Effects Assessment (CEA)
- Climate change impact assessment
- Trade-off for MPA Design
- Trait-based Vulnerability Assessment
- Data sharing
- Strategic guidance
- Prioritising conservation areas

Methods

- Trade-off for MPA Design - Conservation and economic development
- Trade-off for MPA Design - Short-term and long-term benefits
- Trade-off for MPA Design - Exclusives uses and shared uses
- Trade-off for MPA Design - Specific stakeholder interests
- Trade-off for MPA Design - Local and global interests
- Participatory mapping

Tools

In the ESE framework, the term Tool is used to define one specific practical instrument (e.g. a model, an application, a database) that can be applied to specific cases. Tools - also named Decision Support Tools (DSTs) - are based on Methods that represent their conceptual base. Example: Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) is a method to assess cumulative impacts on marine ecosystems. Some tools are available based on CEA: e.g. Tools4MSP CEA, HELCOM SPIA tool, Planwise4Blue. In this Guidance, both Methods and Tools are collectively named as Operational approaches.

- Pressure assessment of MARine activities (PMAR) module
- Tools4MSP CEA
- HELCOM SPIA Tool

- PlanWise4Blue
- CC Analog Base Velocities
- GFW - Global Fishing Watch
- EMODnet
- Area-based Conservation Planner (ABC)

3.5 Answers

In the ESE Framework, each management question is linked to its answer. Answers bring together the ESE framework interconnected components: Practices, Modules, Criteria, Operational approaches, Data, Measures, as described above. This integrated approach ensures that users receive not just generic advice but tailored, actionable solutions that combine methodological rigor, ecological understanding, socio-economic considerations, and policy relevance — helping to fill the gap between science, policy, and practical marine management.

Answers include indication on the following elements to be applied to respond to specific management questions:

- Practices: Structured methodological steps to be undertaken (step-by-step approach), aligned along the management cycle (scoping, data collection and presentation, analysis and diagnosis, prioritisation and designation, implementation and management, and monitoring and evaluation), guide the decision-making process and ensure consistency and rigor.
- ESE Modules: Thematic toolkits (e.g., ESE1, ESE2, ESE3) and policy solutions provide strategic guidance tailored to different management contexts and objectives. Each answer may link to one or more ESE module, allowing for a multidisciplinary approach.
- Criteria: Answers include recommendations on which criteria to apply — spanning from broad classes and groups of indicators to specific single criteria — supporting clear prioritisation and evaluation processes.
- Operational Approaches: Answers identify the methods, and decision-support techniques (DST) appropriate for implementation, ensuring that recommended actions are evidence-based and operationally feasible.
- Data: The framework ensures that relevant and consistent datasets are used, organised according to categories defined in the Marine Spatial Planning Data Framework (MSPdF), covering ecological, socio-economic, governance, and ecosystem service information.
- Measures: Where available, answers reference tested measures and examples of good practices, providing practical insights into how recommended actions can be effectively implemented.

Each answer also provides a conceptual diagram of the steps to be undertaken and how the different elements addressed by the guidance can be used in combination to answer the question (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Example of conceptual diagram provided by the ESE framework for each answer.

3.6 Application examples

The ESE framework and its modules were applied in the six test sites of the MSP4BIO project, in order to answer some selected questions that were considered of prior interest. Some of the results from the application are included in the framework as examples to provide additional guidance to future users.

Application examples are synthesized in the following paragraphs.

3.6.1 Marine Mammals & CC: NW Mediterranean prioritization for 2030

Management question:

Q 10 - How to prioritize marine mammals' species to be protected according to climate change in NW Mediterranean for 2030?

In this example, the management question reflects the managers' need to be supported in the selection of the most accurate methodology to approach the issue and perform the analysis. The geographical and time scale boundaries were well defined by the test site representatives and linked to the biodiversity strategy for 2030, and we know that climate change needs to be considered according to the work previously done by the project partners:

Criterion 1 - Desirable spatio-temporal scale of the analysis (Highlighting the boundaries) application: Projections need to be "Near-Term" (targeting 2030) and encompass the whole Mediterranean Sea basin (so the considered stressor is mainly Sea Surface Temperature regarding actual data availability and level of knowledge about climatic stressors).

Criterion 2 - Type of output application: the expected output should be a metric that could be ranked (score or quantitative indexes) as the main purpose of the question is to compare species vulnerability to CC to prioritize targets and/or management actions for marine mammals' conservation. Trait-based vulnerability assessment is suitable as core method as it aims to evaluate the sensitivity of each species to different stressors (including climate change stressors) and provide a metric (sensitivity score) for comparison. Moreover, a species traits' database is available at test site scale.

Criterion 3 - Expertise/Complexity of the model application: marine mammals are highly moving species that will probably modify their repartition area before presenting the appearance of physical/trait adaptations to climate change. Moreover, near-term questions are less likely to induce evolutionary process. For these reasons, a trait-based vulnerability assessment based only on Sensitivity criteria (e.g. linked to inner traits such as moving capacities or thermal tolerance) is particularly suitable to compare the near-term answers between species and will be selected to feed the macro-criterion Vulnerability in the Analysis and Diagnosis Practices. The selection of a single criterion among the list of criteria available in the ESE platform to feed the Vulnerability macro-criterion will respect the parsimony approach (simple equation) and is considered as leading to an acceptable level of uncertainty in the literature.

Final output of the scoping: in this example, the output of the scoping will be the selection of an analysis method and metric aka the selection of Trait-based vulnerability assessment based only on Sensitivity criteria to sea surface temperature as core analysis.

3.6.2 Application of the HELCOM SPIA Tool for HELCOM MPAs

Management question:

Q 12 - How to evaluate cumulative impacts in MSP and MPA?

The MSP4BIO Baltic Sea test site conducted a comprehensive assessment of pressures and impacts within HELCOM MPAs, using the HELCOM SPIA tool. The objective was to identify the most impacted ecosystem components, the key pressures driving these impacts, and the MPAs most affected.

The analysis revealed that bottom-water habitats not influenced by permanent stratification are among the most impacted components, primarily due to physical disturbance, eutrophication, and hazardous substances. Marine mammals such as grey seals and harbour porpoises are also significantly affected, especially by continuous anthropogenic noise.

Hazardous substances and eutrophication emerged as the **most significant pressures** inside HELCOM MPAs. These pressures largely originate from land-based sources such as industrial discharges and agricultural runoff and illustrate a critical management challenge: while MPAs can regulate human activities within their boundaries (e.g., fishing, tourism), they have limited authority over diffuse pressures originating outside their jurisdictions. Additional relevant pressures include physical disturbance from bottom trawling, the spread of non-indigenous species introduced via shipping, human presence in sensitive areas, and anthropogenic sound disrupting species that rely on acoustic cues for communication and navigation.

The analysis also identified **specific MPAs with the highest levels of cumulative impact**, underscoring that many of the most affected sites are in Germany, Estonia, and Finland.

Overall, this assessment highlights the need for strengthened regional cooperation and integrated management approaches that address external pressures impacting MPAs. Despite their designation, many Baltics MPAs remain vulnerable to pressures beyond their control, emphasizing the importance of linking site-level management with broader regional and international policy frameworks.

3.6.3 An MPA redesign and enlargement proposal for the Graciosa Island Test Site

Management questions:

Q 8 - How to identify and analyze the main conflict area that may arise if we need to expand marine protected areas?

Q 11 - How to integrate socio-economic objectives in assessment of existing MPA (network) and identification of new MPAs?

Q 13 - How to evaluate trade-offs in MSP and MPA designation process?

Q 35 - How to assess and develop scenarios for MPA networks representativeness, ecological coherence, adequacy, comprehensiveness and connectivity, also in transboundary contexts?

Q 53 - How to identify and analyze the main conflict areas between human uses and the environment?

Q 63 - How to deal with knowledge gaps on socio-economic data, including the spatial dimension?

The proposal for Graciosa Island emphasises the application of Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs (ESE2) and Trade-offs method for protections and restoration in MSP and **Nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors (ESE3) in developing a new MPA management strategy**. The final outcome was to present a proposal for an IUCN category VI MPAs, involving the redesign and expansion of a previous existing area. The new design space will protect biodiversity while promoting sustainable fishing and tourism activities in the region.

One of the project's results was the **co-creation of a new map, including fisheries management zones, developed in collaboration with local stakeholders**. This involvement was fundamental, as the Graciosa community emphasised the wish for co-creation and the importance of good management practices in MPAs. These practices are essential for the effective protection of marine resources and the maintenance of environmental quality while ensuring the local community keeps its traditional uses of the ocean.

Integrating effective management practices, promoted through the co-creation with all the agents with an interest in marine management, strengthens the community's confidence in conservation initiatives. This approach not only improves awareness of the importance of MPAs but also emphasises the shared responsibility for protecting local ecosystems to maintain their traditions in place in a sustainable way.

SeaSketch was a vital tool for participatory mapping in this case and in the Azores in general, offering an innovative platform for marine planning and management that enhances stakeholder engagement. By enabling users to clearly and immediately visualise map data, contribute with spatial information, and collaboratively design zoning scenarios such as MPAs, SeaSketch facilitates informed decision-making and promotes shared visions for sustainable ocean management. The Azores' unique marine environment benefits from SeaSketch's ability to integrate diverse datasets (as the ocean Uses Survey to support Azores MSP) and provide advanced geospatial analysis, ensuring that planning processes are inclusive, efficient, and tailored to the region's ecological and socio-economic priorities.

3.6.4 Integrated Management Framework Proposal for the Cadiz Bay Test Site

Q27 - How to create/increase stakeholder knowledge, awareness and engagement on MPAs and MSP?

Q 35 - Are there good practices of MSP-MPA integration in terms of governance?

Q30 - How to demonstrate the effectiveness of conservation measures to stakeholders?

This proposal outlines a **strategic and participatory approach to developing an integrated land-sea management framework for the Bay of Cádiz**. Over the three years of the MSP4BIO project, an inclusive co-creation process unfolded through a series of interactions with the CoP and regional stakeholders. Participation ranged from 10 to 40 individuals depending on the session, with consistently high levels of engagement and commitment to improving the governance of the Bay. Thanks to this deep and collaborative involvement, key governance gaps and needs were identified—such as the absence of participatory structures, weak institutional coordination, and a lack of operational capacity. These insights led to concrete, locally relevant proposals for a more integrated, transparent, and inclusive management system for the Bay of Cádiz. The initiative aimed to **define a shared agenda that integrates ecological, social, and economic priorities across institutions and sectors**. The University of Cádiz plays a key facilitation role due to its perceived neutrality and leadership in current coordination efforts. Inspired by the ICZM strategy in Mar Menor, the proposal includes the creation of a dedicated fund to ensure stable financing of cross-sectoral projects, enabling long-term implementation of the shared goals of the agenda.

A significant challenge identified in Cadiz Bay is fragmented governance, and to address this the shared goals (Cadiz Bay Agenda) is crucial, but not enough. It is needed to increase capacity building in the bay through the creation or reform of existing coordination bodies, fostering regular meetings between administrations, and increased transparency through the publication of meeting minutes. Strengthening ties with the South-Atlantic marine demarcation (one of the MSP areas in Spain) processes and assigning a regional coordinating authority are seen as essential next steps to foster land-sea coordination.

Public participation has traditionally been weak in Cadiz Bay. The proposal suggests transforming participation into cultural engagement by:

- Reforming existing participatory bodies like the Junta Rectora (Natural Park participative body) or creating a new inclusive governance platform for the entire Bay.
- Organizing regular, high-quality participatory meetings
- Promoting training, education, and expert exchange
- Hosting co-creation workshops involving local communities, artists, and scientists

These efforts aim to foster a shared identity tied to Cadiz Bay's natural and cultural heritage, promoting long-term stewardship.

While the ESE1, ESE2, and ESE3 approaches were introduced as part of the MSP4BIO framework, the participatory process in Cadiz Bay revealed that many stakeholders felt it was premature to implement operational tools of this kind. Instead, they emphasized the need to first address existing governance challenges in the Bay. There was a strong call to take a step back and reflect on how decisions are currently made, who is involved, and

what structural changes are needed to enable future implementation efforts. As a result, in collaboration with the MSP4BIO partners responsible for Policy Solutions (Task 6.2), a tailored approach was developed. This new direction focused on strengthening the governance system of the Bay before applying further technical tools. The outcomes reflect a locally grounded understanding that policy and institutional alignment must come first, so that future tools and strategies can be more effective and actionable.

3.6.5 Integration of CEA in MSP by utilising PlanWise4Blue (ESE 1) - Bulgarian Black Sea test site

Management question:

Q 12 - How to evaluate cumulative impacts in MSP and MPA?

PlanWise4Blue comprises a combination of tools, such as Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA), designed to provide insights into various ecological and environmental aspects that are crucial for MSP and sustainable development. It provides user-friendly solutions for the assessment of the cumulative impacts of human activities on diverse natural values and resources.

Three scenarios were explored with CEA for the three vulnerable mobile species, mammals: *Delphinus delphis*, *Phocoena phocoena* and *Tursiops truncatus*:

- Present (Scenario 0): corresponds to current human use conditions (military areas, shipping).
- Scenario 1: analyses cumulative effects of wind farms, aquaculture, representing a future state (planned aquaculture and OWF), while maintaining current shipping and military zones.
- Scenario 2: reflects a scenario in which all human uses remain the same, except shipping intensity is doubled in the same areas.

The information available for fishing is limited and incorporating MPAs into CEA requires careful consideration. MPAs are zones where most of key human activities are restricted or prohibited, so their inclusion would not typically occur within the CEA itself but rather in subsequent integrative analyses as measures to prevent or reduce impacts.

These analyses would integrate CEA results with conservation tools (e.g., MPAs) and other dimensions within a broader MSP framework. It is essential to have a clear understanding of the specific objectives of the conservation measures and, in particular, a semi-quantitative or quantitative assessment of its actual effects on the target species. This is an interesting consideration for a future exercise. Due the coarse resolution of the spatial data for three marine mammals and because they are mobile species, the CEA application goes beyond the test site scope and was extended to the EEZ of Bulgaria.

All three outputs provide a clear gradient of conditions, including the current situation, the inclusion of planned activities, and their intensification, providing informative alternatives for strategic and spatial planning actions.

3.6.6 Prioritization and optimization for the identification of strictly protected Belgian MPAs

Management question:

Q 16 - How to prioritize areas for conservation (designation of new MPAs)?

The MSP4BIO Belgian Part of the North Sea test site focused on identifying priority areas to be considered for strict protection to align with the requirements of the EU biodiversity law (10% strict protection). By using the ABC Planner tool (Kotta et al. 2024), **an area prioritization and optimization analysis was implemented to identify zones for strict conservation, while considering the many other activities that take place in the BPNS.**

Since the new and third MSP (2026 – 2034) in Belgium is currently undergoing finalizations, new proposals cannot be integrated anymore. The proposed planning solution will be used as a validation step where the resulting zones from the prioritization and optimization analysis can be compared to the proposed MPAs and nature restoration areas for the third MSP.

To highlight the importance of current nature conservation zones (Natura 2000 MPAs), Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) were treated as valuable sandbanks in the ABC planner analyses. Additionally, focus was given to potential marine reserves with a higher degree of connectivity. Based on a trade-off analysis that was performed during one of stakeholder workshops using the SeaSketch tool, and available data layers for the BPNS, the following human pressures were used in the ABC scenario analysis: offshore renewable energy, maritime traffic, and fishing intensity.

For offshore renewable energy both current and future concession areas were included, with a higher emphasis on the current concession zones. For maritime traffic, shipping density data was used to identify high-traffic shipping areas (data from 2023 for all vessel types). Lastly, as most significant fishing-related impacts in the BPNS are likely caused by benthic trawling, only those trawling areas with more than five hours of activity were included. The distribution and intensity of these human activities was explicitly considered to avoid establishing conservation areas in locations where high pressures would compromise their effective establishment.

In the ABC planner, the existing nature value (NV) targets were set to 30% of the total protected nature assets, which resulted in just over 10% of the total Belgian EEZ being protected. For biological nature values, the focus was on benthic species. Habitat suitability maps of five key ecological macrobenthic species were used (*Abra alba*, *Magelona Eensis*, *Hesionura elongata*, *Nephtys cirrosa*, and *Macoma balthica*). Sandbanks were restricted to binary values (0 for absence and 1 for presence), and all invertebrate data were normalized to a 0-1 scale. These normalized maps were then averaged to produce a single infauna map, ensuring the habitat's value was better integrated into the analyses.

The proposed marine reserves, covering roughly 10% of the BPNS correspond partially to those proposed for the new MSP ($\pm 4\%$ of the BPNS). The smaller area located furthest offshore identified by the ABC planner corresponds quite well to the offshore zone proposed for the third MSP (2026-2034). The biggest area identified with the ABC planner overlaps mainly with the new concession zones. Although this area corresponds to ecological important habitats with high biological value, as was evident from the nature valuation, the new concession zones have been approved and will be implemented during the third MSP for the BPNS. Only a very small part of this biggest area identified by the ABC planner overlaps with one of the newly proposed zones for the third MSP. Unfortunately, that part also covers heavy traffic lanes. The most coastal zone that was identified by the ABC planner is located right next to the coastal area proposed for the third MSP. The difference between these zones is a trade-off between fishing intensity and natural valuation. The zone proposed by the ABC planner avoids the higher fishing intensity zone while the zone proposed for the third MSP covers an area with a higher biological value.

For a second scenario run with the ABC planner stricter thresholds could be applied on the human uses and trade-offs, and more biological data could be added for nature valuation (e.g. *Lanice conchilega* habitat suitability map and pelagic fish distributions). The results here clearly demonstrate the value of tools like the ABC planner in guiding the designation and optimization of area-based protection measures in regions with a high concentration of human activities.

3.6.7 Deep-sea ecosystems conservation strategy in the NW Mediterranean: a blueprint for 10% of protection

Management question:

Q34 - How to achieve the strict protection area target of 10% by 2030 in marine areas?

The NW Mediterranean test site objective was to identify some conservation priorities to guide the expansion and increase the efficiency of the current Franco-Italian transboundary Marine Protected Areas network. In particular, it aims to start to integrate climate change scenarios and potential shifts in ecological responses in MSP by identifying knowledge and methodological needs to support a better planification of scientific and management efforts. Finally, it endorsed the political target of designating 10% of strictly protected areas (or Strong Protection Zones SPZ regarding the level of protection defined as acceptable according to the 30 by 30 objectives which still need to be defined at the international and test site scale), applied to the deep-sea ecosystems and considering marine mammals and benthic habitats as indicators of outmost importance for their environmental value as well as ecological features receiving prominent political attention. The approach will be precautionary in the sense that it will propose areas under protection even if not all knowledge is available.

Inputs include meetings with the test site CoP in Italy and France, interactions with experts, workshops, the analysis of the existing planning documents and, on the French

side, of the public debate for the revision of the maritime spatial plans, which took place from November 2023 to April 2024.

Scoping

- Management question: how to set up 10% of strictly marine protected areas contributing to the good environmental status of marine ecosystems?
- Management objective: conservation of deep-sea ecosystems
- Management approach: selective
- Context scale: at MSP level
- Geographical area: NW Med with more than 200m depth. It concerns the French vocation map sectors n°1, 18, 19, 20, 21, 27, 28, and the Italian maritime spatial plan sub-areas MO/8_01, MO/8_02, MO/8_03 and the Northern half of MO/11_01.
- Temporal scale: near- and mid-term Human uses: fisheries, maritime traffic, deep prospection
- Human pressures: pollutions, noise, abrasion and resuspension of particles, extraction of species, invasive species, animal disturbance and collision, fishing
- Bio-ecological target: deep-sea habitats, marine mammals, as species engineers (habitats formers) and indicators of vulnerable ecosystems (species - ecosystems priorities for conservation: European Habitats Directive Annex I, II, IV; SPA/BD Protocol Annexes II-III: list of endangered or threatened species; General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean Vulnerable marine ecosystems' indicator features, habitats and taxa, FAO)
- Macro-criteria: vulnerability, functional hotspots, life cycle critical areas, climate smart potential

Data collection and presentation

A map viewer with a selection of information has been set-up specifically for the NW Mediterranean test site ([Map viewer MSP4BIO](#)) for the implementation of participatory mapping (being filled in). A story board (NORTHWESTERN MEDITERRANEAN SEA | MSP4BIO) presenting what is at stake has been developed to inform the general public and raise awareness. The selected information includes areas already identified as important for nature under different environmental policies: Natura 2000 sites and other marine protected areas, Important Marine Mammals' Areas (IMMAs defined by ACCO-BAMS), Ecologically and Biologically Significant Areas (EBSA defined by the CBD), and all Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) information available to date. Other main data displayed are marine mammals' density observed from aerial surveys, marine mammal's species diversity referenced in OBIS sea-map, expert knowledge about the Ziphius (*Ziphius cavirostris*) and the Sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*) preferential areas, and Chlorophyll-a concentration distribution (as proxies of productive areas and upwellings) obtained from Copernicus Marine Service.

Activities considered are fisheries (especially bottom fishing) and maritime traffic. Location of fisheries is represented through Automatic Identification System (AIS) information

from European trawlers more than 15m long and used as proxy of fishing pressure. Maritime traffic is synthetised using AIS data and showing the main routes for the different types of traffic.

Analysis and diagnosis

The analysis relied first on observations data and previous identification of areas of interest. It resulted in six large areas of interest: the slope of the continental shelf in the Gulf of Lion, the coastal area from Port-Cros to Sanremo, the Gulf of Genova, the NW of Corsica and two large areas far offshore, significant in terms of density of marine mammals and Chlorophyll-a mass concentration observations.

Additionally, three areas of particular interest either due to strong cumulative evidence supporting protection or significant public concern expressed during consultations were identified: the W part of the Gulf of Lion Canyons, the Var and the Sanremo Canyons.

Overlaying these areas of interest with activities of fisheries and maritime traffic shows most interactions with fisheries in the western part of the Gulf of Lion, and with maritime traffic in the Eastern part of the Gulf of Lion, as well as in NW and West Corsica.

Connectivity: the main drivers in connectivity are general East to West currents along the slope of the continental shelf. Therefore, it is stressed the importance of eastern sites features strongly influencing the western ones. The designation strategy should then have the precaution to include an East-West profile.

Climate change inclusion will depend notably on the capacity to integrate three conditions: the connectivity at the scale of the sea basin, a large range of depth in a single site to allow distribution shift along the slope, a large range of North-South and East-West areas.

Prioritization and designation

Existing maritime spatial plans in France and Italy already decided general priorities in their vocation maps. They are used to give weight to environmental arguments in the trade-offs compared to other socio-economic criteria. Additionally, in France, the public debate “la mer en débat” (November 2023-April 2024) organised by the National Council for Public Debate, in support to the revision of the maritime spatial plan, focused notably on the development of strictly protected areas. Participatory mapping was organised both through an Internet platform and during public workshops. The synthesis drawn by the National Commission endorses priorities (including deep sea features in Corsica and Côte d’Azur) such as the slope and canyons’ heads of the Gulf of Lion. It also proposes to enlarge the test site and include Spain in the discussions as there are some border conflicts, especially in the fisheries sector, that need to be integrated to ensure an accurate joint protection initiative. It is especially true for the designation and respect of strictly protection areas (e.g. western canyons’ heads) that need to be respected by both side of the border.

As a first step, we propose seven large potential nature reserves that could potentially act as future networks to reach the 10% target. The proposed design could serve as a basis

of reflection for the next round of discussion between decision-makers and stakeholders. The criteria used to identify these potential strictly protected areas were the following:

- Coherence with the local and national conservation initiatives and conventions (i.e. located in the already identified areas of interest and if possible, of particular interest)
- Limiting Trade-off needs (i.e. avoiding, when possible, interactions with existing human activities)
- Coherence with the existing MSP plan outputs (i.e. giving a higher priority to nature protection where the maritime spatial plans are doing so)
- Coherence with the stakeholders' opinion (i.e. valuing the conclusions of the public debate)
- Capitalizing on the existent (i.e. integrating and completing existing protection and strict protection zones such as the National Parks of Port-Cros and Calanques, Bonifacio Strait International Park)
- Looking for synergies, especially with other existing MPAs as well as with terrestrial protected areas connected with the marine compartment to ensure a better inclusion of the land-sea connectivity and protection effort
- Identifying opportunities (i.e. identifying existing Other Effective Conservation Measures where management measures are already existing and can be strengthened (e.g. Fisheries Restricted Area and Particular Sensitive Special Areas)
- Sufficient size to beneficiate to highly moving species (if possible, more than 1000 km² large)
- Position to maximize potential connectivity according to the actual level of knowledge (i.e. integrating West-East and North-South gradients)

Conclusion

The proposed network is theoretically answering to the 10% target at the test site scale by combining available information and considering socio-economic criteria as well as public consultation inputs and already decided maritime spatial priorities. It constitutes a step toward the designation of strictly protected areas. It could be included in maritime spatial plans' revisions as areas where the natural component needs to be prioritized and protected, keeping in mind the benefit expected from the designation of the whole network. Additional information and consultation are necessary to reach the final designations under the proper legal status notably inventories and surveys for more precise habitat mapping and activities appraisal, and discussion with stakeholders directly concerned.

4 Conclusive remarks

The development and implementation of the ESE Framework and its associated web-based tool represent a significant advancement in integrating ecological and socio-economic considerations into MSP processes, particularly in support of MPAs.

One of the main strengths of the framework lies in its ability to connect questions relevant to ecosystem and socio-economic considerations with concrete planning practices, criteria, measures and tools, offering users guided pathways through complex decision-making processes. The modular and question-based structure ensures flexibility and adaptability, making the guidance responsive to different user needs and planning contexts.

To support the structuring and organization of the content, the framework leverages the MSP Data Framework, which provides a coherent schema for categorizing information across ecological, socio-economic, and governance dimensions. This ensures consistency in the way knowledge is collected, referenced, and related to planning needs, improving usability and interoperability across different contexts and users.

In addition, the inclusion of policy solutions complements the set of planning and technical tools by highlighting regulatory and governance mechanisms that can support or enable implementation. These policy solutions cover a wide range of interventions, from legal instruments and institutional arrangements to coordination strategies and incentive schemes and provide users with a broader perspective on how to operationalize ecosystem-socio-economic integration within MSP processes.

To further enhance its practical relevance, the framework includes a set of application/examples, which illustrate how the proposed solutions have been implemented in real-world cases. These examples help to ground the conceptual elements in operational contexts, making it easier for users to understand how different components of the framework can be translated into concrete actions. They also provide inspiration for how similar approaches might be replicated or adapted elsewhere.

The use of a combined web admin interface and a lightweight, modular web tool has proven to be an effective strategy for enabling a participatory and iterative design process. This architecture not only facilitated real-time collaboration among project partners and stakeholders but also ensured the system's potential for continuous content updates and future scalability.

However, some limitations must also be acknowledged. While the lightweight nature of the tool enhances its usability and maintainability, it also imposes constraints in terms of advanced features such as search functionalities, multilingual support, and enhanced interactivity, which may be desirable in the future. Furthermore, the framework's effectiveness depends on the quality and completeness of the content entered, requiring continuous engagement from contributors and feedback from end users.

Looking ahead, several opportunities for further development emerge. The framework is highly transferable and can be adapted to other policy domains or governance contexts

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beyond MPA in MSP, particularly in areas where co-creation, systems thinking, and integrated planning approaches are required. The current structure also allows for new questions, modules, and stakeholder inputs to be incorporated over time, supporting its evolution in response to emerging needs and challenges.

In conclusion, the ESE Framework and included tools provide a solid foundation for advancing the knowledge base and decision-support capacity within ecosystem-sensitive planning processes. With its participatory origin, flexible design, and technical scalability, the framework is well-positioned to support future efforts toward more integrated, adaptive, and inclusive marine governance.

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5 ESE Framework availability

ESE Web Tool	https://ese.tools4msp.eu/
ESE Guidance (PDF)	https://ese.tools4msp.eu/_build/latex/eseframework.pdf
ESE Admin	https://api.tools4msp.eu/admin/

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Annex 1 – ESE framework downloadable document (on 25.07.2025)

This annex includes an excerpt from the ESE Framework guidance document, featuring its cover and table of contents. The complete guidance is accessible as a supporting resource to the present deliverable.

The full document is available at: https://ese.tools4msp.eu/_build/latex/eseframework.pdf

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ESE Framework

Release 1.1

MSP4BIO

Jul 25, 2025

INTRO:

1	Introduction	3
2	MSP4BIO	5
3	Glossary	7
4	Management Needs	11
4.1	Strengthening Conservation	11
4.2	Balancing between economics and conservation	13
4.3	Integrated management of marine ecosystems	13
4.4	Stakeholder engagement, participation, co-creation	14
5	MSP Stages	15
5.1	Starting the process	15
5.2	Assessing the context and defining a vision	16
5.3	Analyzing existing and future conditions	16
5.4	Identifying key issues	17
5.5	Elaborating the plan	18
5.6	Implementing	20
5.7	Monitoring	20
5.8	Assessment	21
5.9	Revision	22
6	ESE Modules	23
6.1	Policy solutions	24
6.2	ESE1 - Ecological toolkit	24
6.3	ESE2 - Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs	25
6.4	ESE3 - Trade-offs method for protections and restoration in MSP	26
6.5	ESE3 - Nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors	27
7	Questions	29
7.1	Q 61 - How can reliability/accuracy of the spatial data for MPA identification be improved?	29
7.2	Q 64 - How to deal with knowledge gaps on impacts of maritime activities, including cumulative impacts?	32
7.3	Q 63 - How to deal with knowledge gaps on socio-economic data, including the spatial dimension?	34
7.4	Q 62 - How to deal with knowledge gaps related to water column data to support establishment of conservation measures offshore?	37
7.5	Q 65 - How can we assess CC impacts on fishing stocks (e.g. cod and sprat) and develop strategies to protect these species across different life stages (e.g. focusing on nurseries and fishing grounds)?	38
7.6	Q 24 - How do MPA policies intersect with MSP?	43
7.7	Q 25 - How to integrate the process of MPA designation or extension in MSP?	46
7.8	Q 27 - Are there good practices of MPA-MSP integration in terms of governance?	50

7.9	Q 26 - How to take OECM into consideration in MSP where no legal instruments are in place?	53
7.10	Q 34 - How to achieve the strict protection area target of 10% by 2030 in marine areas?	57
7.11	Q 38 - How to address ecological functionalities in conservation objectives?	61
7.12	Q 47 - How to address the different scales of management (MSP-MPA) in an ESE framework?	63
7.13	Q 54 - How to anticipate and address climate change within MPA?	64
7.14	Q 55 - How to anticipate and address climate change within a MPA network?	68
7.15	Q 56 - How to anticipate changes in biotopes due to climate change?	71
7.16	Q 57 - How to prioritize areas to be protected in view of climate changes?	75
7.17	Q 60 - What is the impact of CC on deep ecosystems?	78
7.18	Q 59 - What is the impact of CC on marine mammals?	81
7.19	Q 35 - How to assess and develop scenarios for MPA networks representativeness, ecological coherence, adequacy, comprehensiveness and connectivity, also in transboundary contexts?	84
7.20	Q 28 - How to create/increase stakeholder knowledge, awareness and engagement on MPAs and MSP?	87
7.21	Q 29 - How to assess stakeholders' satisfaction in a MSP/MPA process?	89
7.22	Q 32 - How to create a culture of collaboration among MSP, MPA and sector responsible institutions?	90
7.23	Q 30 - How to demonstrate the effectiveness of conservation measures to stakeholders?	90
7.24	Q 31 - How to move from participation to engagement and co-creation, transforming participation in a cultural behaviour?	94
7.25	Q 9 - How to effectively manage conservation areas including both terrestrial and marine zones?	94
7.26	Q 12 - How to evaluate cumulative impacts in MSP and MPA?	97
7.27	Q 53 - How to identify and analyze the main conflict areas between human uses and the environment?	105
7.28	Q 8 - How to identify and analyze the main conflict area that may arise if we need to expand marine protected areas?	108
7.29	Q 11 - How to integrate socio-economic objectives in assessment of existing MPA (network) and identification of new MPAs?	113
7.30	Q 46 - How to identify compensation measures and how to assess their effectiveness?	121
7.31	Q 45 - How to assess economic impacts of conservation measures?	124
7.32	Q 13 - How to evaluate trade-offs in MSP and MPA designation process?	126
7.33	Q 16 - How to prioritize areas for conservation (designation of new MPAs)?	130
7.34	Q 17 - How to identify priority areas for conservation of pelagic biodiversity?	132
7.35	Q 18 - How to identify priority areas for preserving/restoring reef-forming species such as oysters <i>Lanice conchilega</i> or mussels?	135
7.36	Q 6 - What are the priority areas for preserving from climate change effects the reef-former <i>Lanice conchilega</i> ?	139
7.37	Q 37 - How to maintain local retention / population persistence within the MPA?	141
7.38	Q 36 - How to maintain mobile species persistence (and connectivity) and population/community persistence (passive connectivity) across a transboundary MPA?	144
7.39	Q 58 - How to protect vulnerable species against climatic stressors?	148
7.40	Q 33 - What are the environmental legislation/criteria guidance for MPA designation including socio-economic criteria (Commission's SWD, EU Directives, IUCN, new criteria UNCLoS)?	151
7.41	Q 10 - How to prioritize marine mammals' species to be protected according to climate change in NW Mediterranean for 2030?	155
7.42	Q 49 - How to manage cross-border MPAs for cetaceans conservation?	159
7.43	Q 48 - How to reduce risks (e.g. of collision) and impacts (e.g. from noise pollution) on key cetacean species, particularly during the breeding season and in sensitive areas?	161
7.44	Q 7 - How to protect deep Vulnerable marine Ecosystems (VMEs) (strategies, measures, etc.)?	164
7.45	Q 50 - How can deep-water VMEs be effectively identified and conserved with regards to anthropogenic impacts arising from human activities?	167
7.46	Q 51 - How can we minimize the impact of bottom trawling on the growth and survival of gorgonians and other cold water corals located in the NWMED deep-water VMEs?	171
7.47	Q 52 - How to protect pelagic habitats?	174
7.48	Q 41 - What are the main objectives and elements of monitoring programs for MPAs?	177
7.49	Q 43 - How to monitor Ecosystem Services highlighting their linkages to the different high priority socio-economic criteria identified in each site?	181

7.50	Q 42 - What monitoring approach can be taken for extensive MPA networks, especially offshore ones?	185
7.51	Q 39 - What criteria are available to assess sustainability of maritime uses?	188
7.52	Q 14 - How to assess compatibility of maritime uses and MPA conservation objectives? How to prioritize uses?	194
8	Practices	201
8.1	[Not Related to Any Practice]	201
8.2	Scoping	201
8.3	Data collection and presentation	203
8.4	Analysis and diagnosis	204
8.5	Prioritisation and designation	205
8.6	Implementation and management	206
8.7	Monitoring and evaluation	206
9	Policy solutions	209
9.1	Establishing a dedicated coordination framework for marine biodiversity	209
9.2	Utilizing existing groups to establish compulsory biodiversity assessment and reporting mechanisms	211
9.3	Revise MPA objectives and involve MSP authorities in a consultative capacity	212
9.4	Creating continuous input channels for stakeholder engagement in policymaking	214
9.5	Create mandatory, clear measures connecting human activities with biodiversity goals	216
9.6	Strengthening MSP's role in achieving GES through capacity building, trainings and dialogue	218
9.7	Developing comprehensive guidelines and enforcement mechanisms for effective MPA management	220
9.8	Climate-smart maritime spatial planning in EU countries	222
9.9	Allocating maritime tax revenue for national biodiversity strategy	224
9.10	Increase investment in biodiversity research and monitoring for improved policy evaluation	226
9.11	Investing in data collection and decision support tools for planning and monitoring	228
9.12	Applying the policy solutions in the Cadiz Bay	229
10	Criteria classes	235
10.1	1 Ecological and genetic criteria	235
10.2	5 Socio-economic & governance criteria	240
11	Criteria	245
11.1	1.1.1 Vulnerability	245
11.2	1.1.2 Stability	247
11.3	1.1.3 Functional hotspots	249
11.4	1.1.4. Life cycle critical areas	251
11.5	1.1.5 Climate-smart potential	254
11.6	5.1 Socio-economic criteria	256
11.7	5.2 Governance criteria	266
12	Measures	273
12.1	Measures by classification	273
12.2	Measures by sectors	309
13	Operational Approaches	311
13.1	Core methods	311
13.2	Methods	318
13.3	Tools	324
14	MSP Data Framework	335
14.1	MSPdF Data Clusters	335
14.2	Relevance (spatial and temporal)	404
15	Datasets	411

15.1 Marine & Coastal Environment	411
16 Application Examples	413
16.1 Application of the HELCOM SPIA Tool for HELCOM MPAs	413
16.2 An MPA redesign and enlargement proposal for the Graciosa Island Test Site	415
16.3 Marine Mammals & CC: NW Mediterranean prioritization for 2030	417
16.4 Integration of CEA in MSP by utilising PlanWise4Blue (ESE 1) - Bulgarian Black Sea test site	418
16.5 Prioritization and optimization for the identification of strictly protected Belgian MPAs	419
16.6 Deep-sea ecosystems conservation strategy in the North-Western Mediterranean: a blueprint for 10% of	421
16.7 Integrated Management Framework Proposal for the Cadiz Bay Test Site	423
17 Belgian part of the North Sea	427
17.1 Description	427
17.2 Questions	428
18 Baltic Sea basin and Vistula Lagoon/Southern Baltic	431
18.1 Description	431
18.2 Questions	432
19 Gulf of Cadiz	439
19.1 Description	439
19.2 Questions	440
20 Western Black Sea	441
20.1 Description	442
20.2 Questions	442
21 North-Western Mediterranean (NW-MED)	451
21.1 Description	451
21.2 Questions	452
22 Azores Archipelago	457
22.1 Description	457
22.2 Questions	458
23 Overall Statistics on ESE Framework	463
24 Statistics on ESE Questions	465
24.1 Question level	465
24.2 Management needs	466
24.3 Marine zones	466
24.4 MSP Stages	466
24.5 Spatial scales	466
24.6 Test sites	466
24.7 User type	466
25 Indices and tables	473
Index	475